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DIGITALIZATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING THROUGH ELECTRONIC PLATFORMS

In 2020, education around the world faced unprecedented challenges caused by the pandemic. However, teachers withstood the first wave of educational losses with dignity, introducing distance learning and the use of electronic platforms into the educational process. Two years later, when most countries recovered from quarantine restrictions and returned to the normal school schedule, Ukraine experienced a second wave of educational losses due to the hostilities. We have resumed distance learning, but now a significant number of Ukrainian schoolchildren/students who are in the combat zone, in the temporarily occupied territories, or in exile do not have access to even this form of education. So, five years after the active introduction of distance learning, at least in our country, the quality of education is declining, as indicated by almost 70% of parents, teachers, and students. That is why the educational community is concerned about improving the quality of knowledge and learning efficiency. One of the most effective ways to maintain students' cognitive interest and motivation while learning a foreign language is to use electronic platforms that can be used both online and offline, which is why this study is relevant.

The problem of distance education development has been studied by foreign scholars as well: R. Delling, G. Ramblay, D. Keegan, M. Moore, A. Clark, M. Thomson, and domestic researchers: O. Andreev, G. Kozlakova, V. Oliynyk, A. Khutorsky. The use of information technologies in the learning process was considered by: V. Bykov, I. Halytska, R. Hurevych, M. Kademia, N. Morse, K. Obrizana, S. Yatsiuk. However, the specifics of digitalization of foreign language teaching through electronic platforms remain insufficiently studied.

Digital tools, defined as software, applications, platforms, and online or offline resources that can be used with computers, mobile devices, or other digital media, have become a feature of English language learning offline around the world. The digitalization of education has accelerated over the past decade, particularly with the invention of the tablet computer and the widespread availability of high-speed Internet. These developments have given every student the opportunity to have a digital device and access to a range of digital tools [1].

Distance learning technologies present many new opportunities for teaching foreign languages, allowing for an even wider range of teaching methods. It is important to review these distance learning options to distinguish between their different capabilities, as these systems have different limitations on the learning process [2].

Learning a foreign language remotely is a new reality for both teachers and students. Distance learning is versatile and allows you to use any teaching methods

and techniques. Distance learning of foreign languages combines online, traditional and individual learning. The most common forms of learning are video conferencing, online lessons, consultations (group and individual), individual lessons, independent work, project work, and audio recordings. In the context of online learning, there is a need to use tools with the functions of group chats, calls, and conferences provided by Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams [3, p. 13].

The age-specific characteristics of first- and second-year university/college students also require the use of certain distance learning modes; the teacher must take into account the signs of intellectual and psychophysiological development of young people in order to teach English effectively. Nevertheless, the use of electronic platforms can improve the effectiveness of English language learning both online and offline.

Distance learning can be carried out in two modes: synchronous (all participants in the educational process are simultaneously in the web environment) or asynchronous (the educational process is carried out according to a schedule convenient for teachers and students). The difference between synchronous and asynchronous modes is instant messaging and immediate feedback. Asynchronous mode does not allow for this type of interaction.

In choosing a learning mode, a mixed approach is usually optimal, which can help teachers combine the advantages of synchronous and asynchronous modes, online and offline learning [4].

Below are examples of electronic sites and platforms that can help increase students' cognitive activity and thus improve their overall language learning:

- services for creating quizzes, didactic games, presentations and tests on a particular topic: LearningApps, Voki.com, Quizlet.com, Kahoot, Storybird.com, Wordwall;

- services for using photos, videos, images, graphic design for educational purposes: Pixabay.com, Thinglink.com, Canva.com, Bubbl.us, Wordart.com;

- services to improve Internet communication: Bitly.com, Tiny.com;

- services for communication via video, text messages, polls: Zoom Video Communications, Google Meet, Padlet.com, Tricider.com [5].

Thus, the digitalization of all spheres of our lives has increased significantly in recent decades and, of course, education has not been spared. Information technology has provided many new opportunities for teaching foreign languages and allowed us to further expand the range of teaching methods. But over the past five years, humanity has faced a new reality for both teachers and students – learning a foreign language remotely. Online services, electronic platforms, websites for video conferencing, online lessons, consultations, individual lessons, independent and project work, group chats and calls have become a part of the modern teacher's didactic arsenal. Therefore, foreign language teaching will no longer be the usual classroom-based approach, but will combine traditional, distance and individual learning.

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